

Documentation of the Workshop „Good Practice in Bioeconomy Policy Coordination“

held digitally on November 19, 2024

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1. Introduction

This report documents the presentation and discussions of the workshop “Good Practice in Bioeconomy Policy Coordination”. The workshop was held digitally on November 19, 2024, 10-12 am. It was organised as part of the EC-funded coordination and support action “[ShapingBio - Shaping the future bioeconomy across sectoral, governmental and geographical levels](#)” (Slide 1) within the main topic “Policy and Governance” (Slide 2).

ShapingBio The bioeconomy of the future **Horizon Europe Coordination and Support Action**

Objectives

- Better understanding of the EU bioeconomy innovation eco-system
- Evidence-based information
- Recommendations how to strengthen and deploy innovations
- > Revision of EU bioeconomy strategy

36 months
9/2022-8/2025

€ 4 million

10 partners
Coordinator: Dr. Sven Wydra,
Fraunhofer ISI, Germany

9 countries

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Slide 1: *Objectives and key features of the CSA ShapingBio*

ShapingBio
The bioeconomy of the future

ShapingBio study areas, geographical scope and target audience

- All EU countries
- 4 main topics

Policy & Governance

Applied research & technology transfer

Collaboration

Financing

- Close interaction and exchange with all stakeholder groups via various formats

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Slide 2: *Main topics of the ShapingBio project*

The target group of the workshop were bioeconomy policy makers actively involved in bioeconomy policy coordination at national or regional level. The workshop provided a forum for them to engage in moderated discussions with the aim

- to benchmark their own coordination approach against the approaches in other countries or regions
- to identify strengths and weaknesses of the approaches
- to learn from good practice of coordination in other countries and reflect its transferability to their own country or region
- to give feedback to ShapingBio results
- to voice their needs for support to improve bioeconomy policy coordination

The workshop results will feed into ShapingBio policy recommendations (due summer 2025) which will be considered by the European Commission in the revision of the EU bioeconomy strategy.

2. Participants and agenda

Slide 3 gives an overview of the countries and organisations where registered participants work. Most participants come from countries or regions with a dedicated institutionalised coordination group.

Slide 3: Registered participants' countries, affiliations and way of bioeconomy policy coordination

Registered participants' interests for exchange and mutual learning and expectations regarding the workshop are shown in Slide 4.

As 19 policy makers from 10 different countries attended the workshop (31 persons registered), only two instead of three breakout groups were formed (Slide 5). The guiding questions for the breakout group discussions are shown in Slide 6.

Slide 4: *Registered participants' interests and expectations for exchange and mutual learning during the workshop*

Agenda

10:00 – 10:10	Welcome and introduction		
10:10 – 10:25	Presentation of ShapingBio results on bioeconomy policy coordination		
10:25 - 10:45	Questions and comments, plenum discussion		
10:45 – 10:50	Move to breakout group		
	Group 1 National, coordination group	Group 2 National, coordination group and informal exchange	Group 3 National and regional, coordination group and informal exchange
10:50 – 11:55	Exchange on experience and good practice Support needs for improvement	Exchange on experience and good practice Support needs for improvement	Exchange on experience and good practice Support needs for improvement
11:55 – 12:00	Next steps, feedback	Next steps, feedback	Next steps, feedback

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Slide 5: *Workshop agenda*

Work in break-out group

- Tour de table: who is in the group?
- Exchange of experience
- Good practice
- Can good practice be transferred to your situation?
- What would help you to improve coordination in your country/region?
- Comment ShapingBio recommendations

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Slide 6: Guiding questions for break-out group discussions

3. Plenum presentation: Coordination approaches in selected EU countries - strengths, weaknesses and success factors

The plenum presentation gave an overview of selected results from the ShapingBio work on policy and governance. Full and more detailed results can be found in the [ShapingBio deliverable D2.1 \(Hüsing et al. 2024\)](#), freely available on the ShapingBio homepage.

The cross-sectoral, transformative character of bioeconomy makes coordination of bioeconomy policy across different policy fields and ministries extraordinary challenging (Slide 7).

 ShapingBio
The bioeconomy of the future

A holistic bioeconomy policy requires coordination!

Transformative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From linear fossil-based to circular bio-based bioeconomy
Crosscutting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sectors • Policy fields
Knowledge-based, novel value chains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technological, organisational, social innovations • Novel actor constellations
Goal conflicts, stakeholder interests	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agreement on priorities, solutions, compromises • Across sectors, policies, stakeholder interests
Geographical governance levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • „There are many bioeconomies“ • International, EU, Member states, regions, municipalities

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Slide 7: Characteristics of bioeconomy which make policy coordination challenging

However, hardly anything is known about how this coordination is done in practice, beyond those persons directly involved in the coordination. Against this background, an analysis was conducted in Germany, Italy and Estonia on how bioeconomy policy is being coordinated in these three countries (Slide 8). The definition of policy coordination, that was used in this analysis, is given in Slide 9. Two different aspects of coordination were studied (Slide 10):

- The organisational forms in which coordination takes place. They can be located on a continuum between formally established organisational forms, often within hierarchies on the one end of the spectrum, and loose network forms at the other end of the spectrum.
- The way of how interaction takes place during coordination. These interactions can be located on a continuum with negotiations at the one end of the spectrum. Here, the focus is on coming to joint agreements, on finding compromises and also on giving up one's preferred solution for the sake of a

commonly agreed solution. At the other end of the spectrum are consultations with the aim to find solutions which do not interfere with the aims and activities of other ministries, and which avoid conflicts with them.

ShapingBio analysis

- Italy, Germany, Estonia
- How has bioeconomy policy developed over time?
- How is bioeconomy policy coordinated?
 - Key challenges and solutions?
 - Success factors and good practice?
- Which recommendations can be derived?
- Full results in Deliverable 2.1 (end of November 2024)

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Slide 8: *Scope of the ShapingBio analysis of bioeconomy policy coordination*

Definition of policy coordination

Organisations consider positions of other organisations in their own decisions

Capacity to align, integrate and harmonize decisions
across different government entities, in order
to achieve shared policy goals
to agree on ways how to achieve the goals
(e.g. activities, instruments, budget allocation)

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Slide 9: *Definition of policy coordination*

Slide 10: *Organisational forms and way of interaction in policy coordination*

Slide 11 to Slide 15 present the organisational forms for bioeconomy policy coordination in Italy, Germany and Estonia, and located them on the continuum between formally established organisations and networks. Slide 16 gives a comparative overview of the key features and differences of the organisational forms.

Structures

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Slide 11: *Organisational forms of bioeconomy policy coordination in Italy, Germany and Estonia can be located on a spectrum between formally established organisations and networks*

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Slide 12: *Organisational form of bioeconomy policy coordination in Italy: National Bioeconomy Coordination Board*

Slide 13: *Organisational form of bioeconomy policy coordination in Germany: Interministerial working group*

Slide 14: *Organisational form of bioeconomy policy coordination in Estonia: Circular Economy Advisory Steering Group*

Slide 15: Overview of organisational forms of bioeconomy policy coordination in Italy, Germany and Estonia

Main country differences in the organisation of coordination

Criterion	Italy NBCB		
Formal body dedication	Bioeconomy	Bioeconomy	Circular economy
Location of the formal body	„Above“ ministries	Between ministries	Ministry of Environment
Hierarchy in formal body	2 levels: Non-ministerial coordinators members	3 levels: 2 leading ministries 2 actively contributing ministries Passive members	2 levels: Chairperson (Environment) members
Hierarchical level of delegates to body	Medium to high	Low (division)	High (Deputy secretaries of state)
Decision-making competence	Low, preparation of decisions	Low, preparation of decisions	High
Stakeholder inclusion	In formal body	networks	networks

Slide 16: Main country differences in the organisation of bioeconomy policy coordination in Italy, Germany and Estonia

Slide 17 shows that interactions in bioeconomy policy coordination can be located on a spectrum between negotiations and consultation. A negotiation mode seems more appropriate for transformative, strategic topics cutting across different policy fields, but is usually more resource intensive than a mode in which consultations prevail. The latter seems more appropriate for less strategic or sector-specific issues, but might yield more piecemeal solutions than in a mode in which negotiations prevail. Slide 18 gives a comparative overview of key features and differences of both types of interaction modes.

Slide 17: Interactions in bioeconomy policy coordination can be located on a spectrum between negotiations and consultation

	Negotiation ←	→ Consultation
Working climate	Open, constructive, level playing field, communication on equal terms, trustful relationships	Fundamental debates on principles, hierarchical relationships between members
Working mode	Co-development, co-creation, dialogues, personal interaction	Collecting written comments to documents
Mindset	Mindset to find pragmatic solutions give up some of preferred ways of achieving goals	Focus on own goals and preferred ways, agree on lowest common denominator
Meetings, resources	Frequent, regular Resource-intensive	Rare, irregular
Resolution of controversial issues	Within coordination group, by consensus, neutral moderator	Decisions by higher hierarchical levels
Stakeholder involvement	Direct, dialogues, bidirectional top-down and bottom-up interactions	Indirect, unidirectional top-down consultation

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Slide 18: *Characteristics of interactions in coordination by negotiation or consultation*

Conclusions

- Analysis of coordination in 3 countries – 3 different ways of coordination
 - Country-specific rationale, frame conditions, path dependencies why a way of coordination was chosen
 - Country contexts cannot be changed deliberately
 - Transfer of a way of coordination to another country – will probably not work in the same way
 - No identification of a “better/superior way of coordination”
 - Use the presented ways of coordination as benchmark - reflect your own coordination practice
 - Get inspiration what to improve how
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Slide 19: *Conclusions from the ShapingBio analysis of bioeconomy policy coordination*

4. Discussion on bioeconomy policy coordination on national levels – exchange of experience from different EU member states

4.1 Germany

In addition to the information given in the ShapingBio presentation, the following issues were highlighted in the workshop discussions:

The third mandate of the German [Bioeconomy Council](#) ended in 2023. Currently, discussions and negotiations between the responsible ministries are ongoing on a fourth mandate of the council.

A challenge in coordination efforts in Germany is that there are different understandings of the broad concept and term „bioeconomy“, depending on the actor and stakeholder group: Two examples were given to illustrate this: a few German Federal states include red biotechnology and medical and pharmaceutical applications in their bioeconomy definition, whereas this is not the case on the national level. Environmental NGOs have a different understanding of bioeconomy and prioritize different issues than representatives from academia or industry.

In order to better coordinate actions, it is being considered to pick priority areas, clearly define them, determine how the different ministries can contribute to a specific priority area and what their respective roles should be. In this way, a well-coordinated comprehensive cross-government approach to these priority areas could be achieved.

4.2 Italy

In addition to the information given in the ShapingBio presentation, the following issues were highlighted in the workshop discussions:

- The [National Bioeconomy Coordination Board](#) (NBCB) does not only have representatives from all relevant ministries as members, but also independent experts, e.g. scientists. These independent experts ensure continuity and retain the knowledge of previous discussions and activities and can provide consistent advice. This is important because in Italy, governments – and subsequently ministry representatives in the NBCB - change in Italy quite often.
- A major function of the NBCB is information sharing between its members. Regular meetings (approximately 10/year) ensure that NBCB members are up to date regarding recent developments in bioeconomy policy, technology, and regulations.
- Another function of the NBCB, and especially its academic members, is to educate policy makers in bioeconomy concepts which are difficult to understand but are essential for the bioeconomy. An example is the difference between biobased and biodegradable plastics.
- For urgent or specific topics, the NBCB establishes working groups. They also comprise experts and stakeholders. Results and position papers elaborated by these working groups are subsequently discussed and revised in the NBCB until a common position has been reached.
- Current work focusses on the revision and update of the implementation action plan for the Italian bioeconomy strategy BIT II (National Bioeconomy Coordination Board 2021). In a bottom-up approach contributions were collected from major stakeholders. The final document was then edited by a smaller working group. The publication of the revised action plan is expected for February 2025.
- The NBCB also reaches out internationally: Close links have been established with the EC. It was also intensively involved in bioeconomy-related activities during the Italian G7 presidency in 2024. It also

presented the Italian bioeconomy position at the G20 summit in Brazil where agreement on a set of High-Level Principles on Bioeconomy was achieved.

4.3 Estonia

In addition to the information given in the ShapingBio presentation, the following issues were highlighted in the workshop discussions:

Although the coordination was correctly described in the ShapingBio presentation, it very much reflects the situation at a certain point in time, namely the elaboration of a strategic document, the Estonian Circular Bioeconomy Roadmap. As the goal was to advance the concept of bioeconomy in Estonia on the political level, at that time it was the best solution to elaborate the Circular Bioeconomy Roadmap under the umbrella of the Circular Economy Advisory Group (CEAG). This formally established coordination body was composed of representatives of all relevant ministries at high hierarchical levels (Deputy Secretary Generals) with decision-making competence.

However, a drawback lies in the fact that the mandate of the CEAG was circular economy and thus broader than circular bioeconomy. This may lead to situations in which bioeconomy is treated as a minor issue, and other aspects of circular economy are given priority in the discussions and decisions. Another drawback of the high hierarchical level of the CEAG members is that technical or more detailed aspects of bioeconomy cannot be discussed appropriately.

Now that the Circular Bioeconomy Roadmap has been finalised, it is time to rethink the way how coordination between the ministries and between the ministries and stakeholders should be organised. Goals should be to extend the discussions to the wider stakeholder community, and to discuss also more technical and specific bioeconomy issues which are important for bioeconomy deployment.

In a small country like Estonia, many informal ways of communication and exchange between ministries and stakeholder groups have been established and work well. But as the bioeconomy community is so small, the number of formal bodies for different topics is limited. A specific body for bioeconomy would most likely have to rely on the same experts and individuals who would also be involved in a circular economy group.

One option that is currently being considered is the establishment of a bioeconomy hub in Estonia, as part of the BioEast Initiative. This could be the opportunity to revise the current coordination set-up and to find new and effective ways to combine coordination with stakeholders with coordination on the governmental level.

4.4 Ireland

In 2018, the Irish Government published its National Statement on the Bioeconomy (Government of Ireland 2018). In this statement, it decided to establish a High-Level Bioeconomy Implementation and Development Group (BIG). This group is jointly chaired by the Departments of Agriculture, Food and Marine and Communications, Climate Action and Environment. The Implementation Group is crossdepartmental and interagency. The principal task of the Implementation Group is to bring forward recommendations to develop the Irish bioeconomy further and bring policy coherence to all relevant sectors which impact on the bioeconomy in Ireland.

In the first working period of this Implementation Group (2018 to 2022), usually, meetings were regularly held four times a year. Experience collected with cross-departmental collaboration in this period showed that some amendments in the way of coordination should be made. The following coordination challenges were encountered in the BIG:

- Decrease in level of seniority. Work in the Implementation Group was a bottom-up activity which relied on active contribution of its members. However, the hierarchical level of involved individuals decreased.

- Reliance on agencies. The two departments which chair the Implementation Group often required input from agencies which are not directly affiliated to these two departments. In cases where requests from the leading departments were not satisfactorily answered by an agency, it became difficult to enforce the request, as the leading departments had no authority to issue instructions to this agency.

As a consequence, in the phase of implementing the Bioeconomy Action Plan 2023-2025 (Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications et al. 2023), the way of coordination in the group was changed as follows:

- Distribution of leadership for specific tasks. The departments are assigned specific tasks which are core to their key responsibilities and that embed bioeconomy activities more deeply across the activities of the departments. The departments and their agencies have the lead in their specific task.
- Reporting twice a year. All departments are required to report twice a year on their tasks, how they implement bioeconomy themselves and how they intergrate it into their policies to the departments which chair the group.

This change has improved the relationships between the group member departments and the chairing departments. On the one hand, agencies respond better to requests from the departments to which they are affiliated. On the other hand, the chairing departments can better reflect on the actions of all departments and rather leverage activities that the departments are willing to undertake than putting the focus on negotiations for further development.

Coordination meetings take place four times a year, either in person or in hybrid mode to allow for good attendance. Usually, a structured approach is taken in these meetings: the focus is on one of the seven pillars of the Bioeconomy Action Plan 2023-2025 and a deep dive is taken with the responsible department and its agencies.

In addition to the Bioeconomy Implementation and Development Group, The Irish Bioeconomy Forum is a separate experts forum which provides bioeconomy to stakeholders' expertise.

It is planned to develop a National Bioeconomy Strategy for Ireland in 2026, after a process of reflecting the revised EU bioeconomy strategy which is expected by the end of 2025.

Currently, there is transition to a phase where priority areas are being identified, e.g. considering a biomanufacturing roadmap. For this priority area, it will be determined how the different ministries can contribute and what their respective roles should be, e.g. feedstocks (Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine), industry support (Department of Business, Enterprise and Innovation), demand-side approaches such as standards and certification (Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications). In this way, an integrated cross-departmental approach for this priority area should be achieved.

4.5 Finland

In 2020, the Finnish Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment launched a 2-year project to update the Bioeconomy Strategy. The revised strategy was published in 2022 (Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment et al. 2022).

For this strategy process, the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment appointed a steering group, a coordination secretariat and a national Bioeconomy Panel (Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment et al. 2022, p. 50):

The steering group was chaired by the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment. It included representatives from the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment, Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, Ministry of the Environment, Ministry of Education and Culture, Ministry of Social Affairs and Health, Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Transport and Communications, Prime Minister's Office.

Tasks of this steering group comprised

- steering the overall progress of the bioeconomy strategy update,
- deciding on the necessary studies and other measures,
- presenting proposals on the objectives and limitations of the strategy, and
- outlining the key guidelines for the preparation of strategy work.

The Coordination Secretariat was responsible for the practical progress and timetable of the strategy update as well as for writing the actual updated bioeconomy strategy. The Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment, the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, the Ministry of the Environment, the Ministry of Education and Culture, the Ministry of Social Affairs and Health and the Ministry of Transport and Communications were all represented in the secretariat.

The Bioeconomy Panel had the role of an advisory body. Approximately sixty different organisations were represented in the panel. The panel participated in the preparatory work of the revised strategy and stakeholder dialogues, with the aim to get the entire field to commit to the objectives and implementation of the strategy.

Due to changes in government and government priorities, in the current legislative period, there is no formally appointed steering or coordination group anymore. Also, the Bioeconomy Panel is no longer operational. The secretariat still exists, and the three main ministries (Economic Affairs, Agriculture and Forestry, Environment) continue to collaborate on regular, almost daily basis. So, intensive and lasting relationships between the ministries and between ministries and stakeholders had been established which still work, even in the absence of formal coordination bodies. Nevertheless, it is still being considered to establish a Bioeconomy Panel again, but more resources (staff, budget) would be required for this.

The measures to increase the value added of bioeconomy include implementing an RDI programme for the green transition of bioeconomy, and promoting the establishment of innovative pilot and demonstration facilities and the first industrial-scale plants in Finland. Regions are also encouraged to formulate action plans for the bioeconomy (Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment et al. 2022).

4.6 France

In 2017, France adopted its national bioeconomy strategy which structures the development of the bioeconomy for the next 20 years (French Government 2017). The strategy was developed by the ministries in charge of agriculture, the environment, the economy and research, as well as contributions from all stakeholders (e.g. economic players, public institutions, researchers, civil society). An action plan 2018-2020 for operational deployment of the bioeconomy in France was published in 2018 (Ministry of Agriculture and Food 2018). A steering committee was set up when the action plan was initiated in February 2018 which provides administrative staff and professionals from the sector.

The Bioeconomy Cross-Sector Thematic Commission (CTI), set up by FranceAgriMer in 2019, is the national governance mechanism for coordination and monitoring of the bioeconomy development and for the implementation of the national bioeconomy action plan. The CTI has established several working groups (European Commission et al. 2021). During the workshop, the view was expressed that bioeconomy research questions are not sufficiently addressed by the CTI. Therefore, it is planned to establish an informal group with research experts and ministry representatives to elaborate a French position specifically on research issues. Results from this group could be fed into e.g. discussions of the CBE JU state representatives group.

4.7 Poland

Poland does not yet have a dedicated bioeconomy strategy or action plan. However, in the frame of the Coordination and Support Action [CEE2ACT](#) the [Polish Bioeconomy Hub](#) was founded in 2023. Founders of

this hub are the Polish State Research Institute Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation [IUNG](#), the consulting firm [EPRD](#) Office for Economic Policy and Regional Development Ltd., and the NGO Foundation for Education and Social Dialogue [Pro Civis](#).

The function of this Hub is to serve as a focal point for the support the development of a bioeconomy strategy, develop business models and jointly perform activities to develop the bioeconomy. The [operations of the Hub](#) are supported by activities planned within the CEE2ACT project. At present, the Hub brings together appr. 100 representatives from about 20 organisations from different bioeconomy sectors. It promotes bioeconomy at key events. Using a bottom-up approach, key thematic areas in the bioeconomy were selected and prioritised and thematic group leaders were appointed. The thematic groups will create development scenarios for their respective groups and implement the defined goals.

5. Discussion on vertical bioeconomy policy coordination across geographical governance levels - exchange of experience from different EU member states

5.1 Exchange with the European Commission and with other international activities

Good links with the EC have been established by all countries represented in the workshop. However, due to recent changes in the Directorates General responsible for the revision of the EU bioeconomy strategy, countries have to adapt their networking and communication activities accordingly.

Fora for exchange of experience, such as the European Bioeconomy Policy Forum, are perceived as valuable.

The EU bioeconomy strategy is seen as important groundwork and reference for all EU member states. It provides high level priorities and topics, and EU member states take these priorities and topics into consideration and adapt them when developing or revising bioeconomy strategies in their own country.

Several issues crucial for bioeconomy can only be solved at the European, not at member state level. Examples are the legislative framework, standards, or rules in different (sectoral) support schemes with relevance for bioeconomy (e.g. structural funds, Common Agricultural Policy). Coordination between member states and EC level is important to achieve coherence, harmonisation of rules for bioeconomy support schemes and for providing member states' positions to the EC.

Establishing groups of like-minded countries was reported as good practice for supranational coordination, e.g. with Nordic countries, or the BioEast Initiative. Common challenges can be addressed which is perceived as an added value to all group members.

Coordination on supranational level beyond the EU, e.g. in the context of G7, G20, OECD, is also important. These activities stimulate the national discussions and the sharing of best practices.

5.2 Fostering regional engagement in bioeconomy

The following experience with regional engagement in bioeconomy was shared during the workshop:

Italy

Regions and autonomous provinces are represented in the NBCB. These regions differ substantially in the extent and scope of their bioeconomy activities. One of the challenges we face is that we do not have good, robust and consistently applied indicators and data for describing the bioeconomy on regional level and for demonstrating its impact. To show the impact would, however, be very important in fostering regional engagement in bioeconomy, to convince regional policy makers and stakeholders, and also to benchmark the achievements in different regions. It is suggested that EU member states and regions team up with the [JRC Knowledge Center for Bioeconomy](#) to provide input and coordinate efforts, to the benefit of all member states and regions.

Estonia

Up to now, the focus of activities has been on the national level. It has been recognized that it is important to engage regions and even municipalities more in bioeconomy and policy development and to give them more influence. However, these activities are still in an infant stage: In 2024, a pilot activity was carried out to develop regional bioeconomy roadmaps. It turned out that it was not yet possible to speak about bioeconomy in more detail on the regional/local level: on the one hand, knowledge of what bioeconomy is and what it could mean for the region is still low. On the other hand, it still needs to be sorted out which issues and questions should be decided and solved at the national level, and which at the regional or municipal level

Ireland

One of the pillars of the Irish national bioeconomy action plan (Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications et al. 2023) focuses on communities, regions and cities. In this pillar, the action plan sets out actions to support local and regional bioeconomies by enhancing governance approaches, harnessing existing funding opportunities, and boosting social and regional enterprises and skills.

Efforts are ongoing to strengthen the engagement of the three Irish regions in bioeconomy. These regions were invited to the Irish Bioeconomy Forum (2018–2022), and one region participated. As part of the EU-funded project [ROBIN](#), the Southern Regional Assembly and the Munster Technological University joined forces. They engage with stakeholders to develop a governance approach which is appropriate for that region.

Findings and lessons learnt from this project will be discussed with other regional assemblies with the aim to encourage them to elaborate their own governance approach.

The National planning and investment frameworks now include bioeconomy components, and regions are expected to align with them. On the municipal level, funding is provided for research on urban bioeconomy initiatives. Smart specialisation national funding is provided to some bioeconomy initiatives led by local authorities, like innovation centres, living labs or biorefining pilot activities. These efforts help connect higher education institutions and municipalities, fostering a movement that blends bottom-up and top-down approaches. Currently, the best mechanisms are being explored how to build on people's initiatives and interests. For driving these activities, it has been helpful that each municipality now has local biodiversity and climate officers and action plans, and start to have local circular economy plans. These are entry points and sites where the bioeconomy concept can be integrated, so that more people take up bioeconomy topics.

6. Comments to the ShapingBio recommendations

ShapingBio recommendations

- Continue towards a **holistic bioeconomy strategy and policy** which integrates traditional sectoral policy silos
- Strive for „better“ **strategies and action plans which give clearer guidance** for subsequent policy implementation
 - e.g. clear/quantitative goals, clear priorities, shared solutions to goal conflicts, responsibilities, time schedule, budget, measures with concrete policy instruments
- **Institutionalise** bioeconomy policy coordination permanently
- Adopt **multi-actor co-creation approaches**, establish a collaborative, open, trustful working climate to find compromises and exploit synergies
- Actively **learn from good practice**
 - Broaden the knowledge of options, potential pitfalls, success factors, good practice
 - Advocate for/conduct studies, projects, initiatives
 - Actively engage in bioeconomy policy networks and projects (e.g. EU Bioeconomy Policy Forum, OECD, BioEast Initiative, EU CSAs, ...)

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Slide 20: Draft recommendations from the ShapingBio analysis of bioeconomy policy coordination

Participants agreed with the presented ShapingBio recommendations and assessed them as relevant and important.

Participants highlighted the importance of fora and platforms for exchange of experience, good practice and for mutual learning.

Regarding the recommendation to establish formal coordination bodies, the following remarks were given:

Institutionalising coordination helps to coordinate the policy regularly and with clear goals. If it is not institutionalised, coordination may be irregular and not very active. Key success factors are a trustful working climate, a mindset to develop solutions and that discussions result in activities, which have impact and really change and improve the situation. However, formal and institutionalised coordination and exchanges do not always work: building trust is always more difficult in formal settings. If institutionalisation only means to meet a few times a year, but nothing happens after the meetings, it is not the better solution than a non-formalised, non-institutionalised exchange.

7. Participants' feedback

After the workshop, four participants gave the following feedback via the provided feedback form:

	Feedback by participants
Overall rating of the workshop	Excellent: 3 Good: 1
I liked about the workshop	Very useful presentation, analysis and reflections Experience exchange Open formula of the workshop, the possibility to both learn from others and share my experiences. The presentations at the beginning were interesting and set the ground for the discussion Good moderation
I did not like about the workshop	Limited attendance It should have been longer No answers: 2
Helpfulness of the workshop for my bioeconomy-related work	Extremely helpful: 1 Very helpful: 1 Moderately helpful: 2
Rating of the organisation of the workshop	Excellent: 3 Good: 1
Rating of exchange and networking opportunity in the workshop	Excellent: 2 Good: 1 Average: 1
Workshop met expectations Why?	Yes: 4 Very useful presentation, analysis and reflections I was there to learn about the bioeconomy policy coordination and management in the EU countries No reasons given: 2
Likelihood of attending another ShapingBio workshop or event	Very likely: 2 Likely: 2
Suggestions for improvement	More participants, conclusion session after the discussion part Maybe you could provide some documents before the workshop, for example some project's deliverables (if they can be shared) or some policy papers No answer: 2
Recommend this type of workshop to others	Yes: 3 No answer: 1

8. ShapingBio workshop team and contact

The graphic features a large, stylized leaf background. On the left, logos for Fraunhofer ISI, eAgasc (Agriculture and Food Development Authority), and APRE (Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea) are listed. On the right, the workshop team members are listed by country: Germany (Bärbel Hüsing, Piret Fischer, Sven Wydra), Ireland (Noha Mahmoud), and Italy (Francesca Santaniello, Flavia Marucci). The ShapingBio logo is in the top right corner. At the bottom, it says 'Funded by the European Union', 'Grant agreement no. 101060252', and 'www.shapingbio.eu'.

ShapingBio workshop team

Fraunhofer
ISI

eAgasc
AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY

APRE
Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea

Germany Bärbel Hüsing, Piret Fischer, Sven Wydra

Ireland Noha Mahmoud

Italy Francesca Santaniello, Flavia Marucci

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